

THE IMPORTANCE OF HYGIENIC AND SOCIAL FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPLICATIONS OF DOMESTIC INJURIES AMONG SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Domestic injuries among children remain one of the most significant medical, social, and sanitary-hygienic problems worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), childhood injuries not only result in high rates of disability and mortality but also impose a substantial economic burden on families and healthcare systems. Injury incidents negatively affect children's health and are characterized by a high risk of severe complications and long-term disability. Therefore, studying the social and hygienic factors influencing the occurrence of injuries among school-aged children and improving preventive measures is an important public health priority.

Relevance:

Domestic injuries among children remain one of the most significant medical, social, and sanitary-hygienic problems worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), childhood injuries not only result in high rates of disability and mortality but also impose a substantial economic burden on families and healthcare systems. Injury incidents negatively affect children's health and are characterized by a high risk of severe complications and long-term disability. Therefore, studying the social and hygienic factors influencing the occurrence of injuries among school-aged children and improving preventive measures is an important public health priority. Children's age and sex characteristics, the sanitary-hygienic conditions of their living environment, and the level of parental supervision are among the main social factors determining the risk of injury. From this perspective, a scientific assessment of domestic injuries among school-aged children, taking into account the regional characteristics of the Khorezm region, is of considerable importance.

Objective

To comprehensively assess the sanitary-hygienic and social risk factors contributing to the occurrence of domestic injuries among school-aged children.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in general secondary schools located in Urgench city and the Yangiariq and Kushkupir districts of the Khorezm region. Using social-hygienic, statistical, and analytical methods, a specially designed questionnaire survey was administered to 1,106 school-aged children. Information regarding the type of injury, place and time of occurrence, seasonal distribution, age and sex characteristics of the children, and their living conditions was collected and analyzed.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of the gender distribution revealed that the majority of injury cases occurred among boys, accounting for 56.8% (628 children), while girls constituted 42.9% (474 children). The highest injury risk was observed among adolescents aged 10–14 years, representing 48.4% (535 cases) of all recorded injuries. The corresponding figures were 18.4% (204 cases) among children aged 6–9 years and 31.7% (351 cases) among those aged 15–17 years. This finding may be explained by the higher physical activity levels and greater tendency toward risk-taking behavior among boys and adolescents.

The following information was obtained when the localization of the injury and local environmental conditions were studied:

Place of Injury Occurrence	Number of Children	Percentage
Outdoor environment (street)	405	36.62%
Home environment	395	35.71%
Educational institution (school premises)	154	13.92%
Sports activities	58	5.24%
Road traffic environment	53	4.79%
Physical education classes	40	3.62%

The findings indicate that streets and home environments are the primary locations where injuries occur among children. This suggests insufficient adherence to safety regulations within living environments and inadequate supervision during children's leisure time.

Regarding the nosological structure of injuries, bone fractures (35.35%) and soft tissue contusions (30.65%) were the most common types. Other injuries included abrasions and scratches (10.40%), lacerations (7.87%), and thermal burns (3.62%). Although thermal burns were less frequent, they were associated with prolonged hospitalization and severe social and aesthetic consequences. The highest incidence of injuries among schoolchildren was recorded during the summer season (39.15%), whereas the lowest incidence occurred during winter (15.46%). During the day, the peak frequency of injuries was observed in the afternoon (37.3%). This finding may reflect a reduction in family and social supervision during holidays and after-school hours.

Conclusions. Life-related injuries among school-age children are more common among boys, with a maximum prevalence in boys (56.8%) and during active adolescence (10–14 years). In the microsocial environment, home and street conditions (more than 72% in total) are considered the most dangerous zones, and sanitary and hygienic control and strengthening of the home safety environment are required in these places. To prevent injuries, it is necessary to increase the sanitary culture of parents in schools and neighborhoods, and to implement targeted preventive programs aimed at forming safe behavioral skills in children.

